

Still fit to drive? – How Car Sickness affects Takeover and Driving Performance

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Abstract: In automated driving the driver is likely to experience car sickness when not paying attention to the road. Considering previous findings of cognitive performance decrements due to motion sickness, and the fact that driving demands cognitive resources, the aim of this study was to understand if and how car sickness affects takeover and subsequent driving performance. $N = 33$ participants took part in this test-track study with a wizard-of-Oz vehicle including a car sickness condition and a control condition without experiencing car sickness in randomised order. In both conditions four takeover requests were triggered, after which participants performed four different driving tasks. Subjective measures of car sickness, criticality, mental workload, and performance were recorded, as well as objective performance and driving measures. Results of the subjective data showed that takeovers and driving with car sickness were perceived as significantly more critical and demanding compared to without, and that most participants felt impaired by car sickness while driving. These results will be validated with the objective data.

1. Introduction

With the introduction of automated driving (SAE Level 3 and above; SAE, 2021), the role of the driver will change to that of a (part-time) passenger with the possibility of engaging in non-driving related tasks (NDRTs). Among passengers, especially when performing NDRTs, car sickness, a subtype of motion sickness, is a common phenomenon (Rolnick & Lubow, 1991; Schmidt et al., 2020). Therefore, the risk of experiencing car sickness in automated driving will increase, resulting in a potentially car sick driver when taking over control of the vehicle.

Previous studies on the effect of motion sickness on task performance have revealed impairments in cognitive performance, such as increased reaction times (Bos, 2015; Smyth et al., 2019), impaired hand/arm coordination (Smyth et al., 2019), reduced performance on visual search (Golding & Kerguelen, 1992) and perception task (Kaplan et al., 2017). Regarding the effect on driving performance, studies on the effects of simulator sickness have shown prolonged braking reaction times (Reinhard, Tutulmaz, et al., 2019) and reduced average speed (Gálvez-García et al., 2020; Reinhard, Kleeer, et al., 2019). However, to the authors' knowledge there are no studies investigating the effects of car sickness on driving performance in the real world in context of automated driving

including takeover performance. The previously reported performance degradations under motion sickness could lead to safety critical behaviour in complex takeover situations, such as construction sites or obstacles ahead, which require a quick understanding of the situation, as well as appropriate decisions and reactions. Therefore, the aim of this study was to investigate the effects of car sickness on takeover and driving performance in a real-world setting.

2. Method

2.1 Experimental design

A wizard-of-Oz test track study was conducted in which participants experienced two test conditions on separate days and in a randomised order. Symptoms of car sickness were induced in the car sickness condition but not in the control condition. In both conditions, participants had to take over vehicle control four times and perform the four following driving tasks in randomised order after each takeover while sitting on the driver's seat: slalom with a fixed speed (25 km/h), slalom with a freely chosen speed, target braking and two emergency stops upon a warning tone. The target braking required the driver to accelerate to 30km/h and then to stop as accurately as possible at the target position.

Fig.1. Test track with pylons set up to mark the driving tasks (emergency braking on a random spot on each straight)

2.2 Test environment and set-up

The study took place on a closed test track (see Fig. 1). The wizard vehicle was an AUDI Q7 with a conventional steering wheel and pedals on the front left. In addition, the vehicle had instructor pedals on the front right and a joystick to steer the vehicle. The wizard could trigger a takeover request (TOR). Participants had to press a button to confirm the takeover before they could drive themselves.

2.3 Test conditions and procedure

To induce car sickness in the car sickness condition, the wizard simulated a dynamic automated ride including a stop-and-go scenario on the one straight of the test track and a slalom back on the other straight. Participants had to play a maze game (Cabbiegames, 2022) on the smartphone during the ride to increase the likelihood of car sickness (see Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Participant engaging in the NDRT and wizard driving with the joystick on armrest (arrow)

Every 30 s, participants had to verbally indicate their current level of car sickness on the Misery Scale (Bos et al., 2005). The TOR was triggered after 10 minutes or when the participant indicated a MISC level of 7 (mild to moderate nausea). In the control condition, the participants did not experience an automated drive but played the game in standstill for the same time and the wizard drove off a few meters to trigger the TOR. After taking over, participants had to perform one of the driving tasks. Afterwards, a break of at least 6 minutes began, in which participants completed the MSAQ (Gianaros et al., 2001) and questionnaires regarding the takeover and driving task. After the break, the same procedure was repeated for the remaining three driving tasks.

2.4 Test sample

33 subjects (17 female), who were selected based on their moderate to severe susceptibility to car sickness, participated in the study. The mean age was 41.9 years ($SD = 15.5$).

2.5 Dependent measures

To measure the subjective criticality of each takeover and driving task, the Criticality Scale by Neukum and Krüger (2003) from 1=harmless to 10=uncontrollable was used. To assess the mental workload of each driving task an adapted version of the NASA-TLX Questionnaire was applied (Hart & Staveland, 1988).

In a short interview at the end, the participants were asked whether they felt impaired when driving and whether they had adapted their driving behaviour due to car sickness. In addition, objective measures of the takeover and driving performance as well as driving dynamics were recorded, which were still under analysis at the time the abstract was submitted.

3. Results

In 78.5% of all car sickness rides, a MISC level of 7 was reached. Accordingly, the MSAQ scores were significantly higher for all driving tasks in the car sickness condition compared to the control condition (manipulation check). All statistic values of the conducted t-tests can be found in Table 1. The criticality of all four takeovers and of three driving tasks (all except for slalom free) differed significantly between conditions with higher ratings in the car sickness condition (see Fig. 3). In both conditions, the average criticality of takeovers was assessed within the range of harmless.

Fig. 3. Criticality per driving task for both conditions (a) Of takeovers, (b) Of driving tasks

Mental workload was rated significantly higher for all driving tasks with car sickness than without. 72.7% of all participants reported feeling impaired by symptoms of car sickness when performing the driving tasks. Cognitive impairments were mentioned most frequently, such as decreased concentration, orientation and attention or slower

Table 1: Statistics of *t*-tests and descriptives of MSAQ, NASA-TLX and criticality of takeover and driving task

Task	Measure	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>M (SD)</i> car sickness	<i>M (SD)</i> control
target braking	MSAQ*	<i>t</i> (32) = 9.94	<.001	40.27 (15.39)	13.71 (3.52)
	NASA-TLX	<i>t</i> (32) = 5.60	<.001	33.56 (16.84)	20.93 (12.27)
	criticality takeover	<i>t</i> (32) = 4.48	<.001	3.30 (1.83)	1.91 (1.31)
	criticality driving task	<i>t</i> (32) = 3.57	.001	3.18 (2.19)	1.70 (1.19)
slalom free	MSAQ*	<i>t</i> (31) = 10.91	<.001	40.63 (14.28)	13.99 (3.71)
	NASA-TLX	<i>t</i> (31) = 3.06	.005	33.28 (17.39)	26.39 (14.34)
	criticality takeover	<i>t</i> (31) = 3.74	.001	3.28 (1.55)	2.22 (1.68)
	criticality driving task	<i>t</i> (31) = 1.73	.094	3.16 (1.89)	2.50 (1.70)
emergency braking	MSAQ*	<i>t</i> (31) = 9.62	<.001	39.92 (15.20)	14.66 (5.05)
	NASA-TLX	<i>t</i> (31) = 4.36	<.001	37.54 (21.83)	22.57 (8.42)
	criticality takeover	<i>t</i> (31) = 4.99	<.001	3.67 (1.90)	2.00 (1.32)
	criticality driving task	<i>t</i> (31) = 5.14	<.001	3.73 (2.27)	1.78 (0.98)
slalom 25km/h	MSAQ*	<i>t</i> (32) = 9.95	<.001	41.15 (15.27)	14.44 (5.16)
	NASA-TLX	<i>t</i> (32) = 4.45	<.001	40.91 (18.90)	28.73 (17.65)
	criticality takeover	<i>t</i> (32) = 4.40	<.001	3.48 (1.87)	1.94 (1.14)
	criticality driving task	<i>t</i> (32) = 3.41	.002	4.27 (2.28)	3.03 (1.96)

*possible min = 11.11

reaction time. 69.7% of all participants stated that they have adapted their driving behaviour due to car sickness. A lower speed and a more defensive driving style were the most often stated adaptations.

4. Discussion

The results on the level of car sickness showed that the manipulation has worked, i.e. car sickness was considerably induced. All takeovers and driving tasks with speed or braking instructions were rated significantly more critical when driving under car sickness. In the slalom, where participants were free to choose their speed, criticality was not significantly higher with carsickness. It is likely that participants adjusted their speed to make this driving task less demanding. Some participants consistently stated that they reduced their speed and drove more defensively due to car sickness, which is in line with the results of the simulator studies mentioned above (see 1. Introduction). Safety is unlikely to be compromised by reducing speed and driving defensively in an appropriate manner. However, a significant proportion of the sample felt impaired by car sickness while driving, mainly due to reduced cognitive performance, like e.g., slower reaction time or reduced attention. These findings are consistent with previous findings on the effects of motion sickness on performance (e.g., Bos, 2015; Smyth et al., 2019). Such impairments can in fact be safety critical if, for example, obstacles are detected too late or the braking is delayed in emergency situations. However, so far, the results of the present study are based on subjective reports only. It is of interest to check whether the participants' subjective assessments are reflected in the objective measurements. Results on this aspect will be available at the time of the conference and can be presented.

5. Conclusions

In conclusion, driving with symptoms of car sickness is perceived as more demanding, critical and impairs subjective driving performance. Further analysis will be done to verify these findings with objective performance measures.

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